

THE ROLE OF MOTIVATION IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE ACQUISITION: A LITERATURE REVIEW

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Introduction

Acquiring a foreign language necessitates motivation, which serves as a vital component in the learning process. This motivation fosters learner engagement, devotion, and endurance, thereby driving them towards their language learning objectives. In this literature review, we will delve into the various theories and research findings that pertain to the relationship between motivation and foreign language acquisition.

Self-Determination Theory

Self-Determination Theory (SDT) posits that intrinsic motivation is derived from three essential psychological needs: competence, relatedness, and autonomy. In accordance with SDT, those who possess a high level of intrinsic motivation when learning a foreign language perceive it as enjoyable and fulfilling. In contrast, individuals driven by extrinsic motivation are motivated by external incentives or the aim of avoiding penalties.

Achievement Goal Theory

Based on the theoretical framework of Achievement Goal Theory (AGT), there are two primary motivational orientations: task orientation and ego orientation. Task-oriented individuals are motivated by a desire to acquire language proficiency and attain competence, while ego-oriented individuals are driven by the need to demonstrate their superiority over others. Research findings indicate that task orientation is more strongly linked to foreign language achievement than ego orientation, according to AGT.

Goal Theory

The fundamental principle of goal-setting is to establish clear and ambitious targets, which promotes motivation and encourages language learners. By setting goals specific to acquiring a foreign language, learners are more likely to engage in self-directed learning and demonstrate determination in surmounting hurdles.

Social-Cognitive Theory

The Social-Cognitive Theory (SCT) is centered on the impact of social elements on motivation. It posits that learners' motivation is influenced by their perceived

self-efficacy, their beliefs about the significance of language learning, and the level of support they obtain from others.

Other Motivational Factors

In addition to the previously mentioned theories, studies have discovered other elements that contribute to the motivation of language learners, including:

Interest: Individuals who are fascinated by the target language or culture are generally more driven to acquire it.

Attitudes: Positive attitudes towards foreign language learning can enhance motivation.

Anxiety: High levels of anxiety may impede motivation by erecting obstacles to learning.

Culture: Cultural values and beliefs can have an impact on learners' motivation to learn a foreign language.

Implications for Language Teaching

Understanding the role of motivation is crucial for language teachers. They can create motivating learning environments by:

Fostering intrinsic motivation by making learning enjoyable and meaningful.

Setting challenging but achievable goals.

Providing autonomy and support to learners.

Creating a positive and encouraging classroom culture.

Incorporating culturally relevant materials and activities.

Conclusion

One of the key factors in acquiring proficiency in a foreign language is motivation, which is a critical and multifaceted element that must be carefully considered. Language instructors can nurture productive learning environments by immersing themselves in the numerous theories and research studies on motivation, which can inspire learners to take a more proactive role and exert greater effort, ultimately leading to more substantial achievements.

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